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THE REVIEW OF BENEFITS EXTENSIVE READING AND INTENSIVE READING IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN ESL/EFL CLASSES

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Annotation. Reading is the receptive skill, that helps students in many ways, not only in acquiring language, but in different spheres. There are specifically two ways of reading: extensive and intensive. The purpose from this article is to discuss extensive and intensive reading, its benefits in our reading process.

Keywords: reading, benefits, extensive, intensive.

INTRODUCTION

Reading is the process of interpreting the written language, to acquire any knowledge, in other words this is the exchange of the ideas, someone's opinion and experiences and information about anything in written form. By reading people find out the new knowledge, information, travel to one's inside world that is written.

Reading is the process of comprehending a transcribed text by identifying the letters and visually evaluating them. It can also mean converting into noises. Both personally and socially, reading is significant. Social reading enhances a person's thinking, conduct, and interpersonal connections and aids in environment adaptability. One's perspective on the world is improved and their degree of appreciation is raised through personal reading. The basic goal of reading comprehension is to help students understand what they are reading, give words meaning, expand their vocabulary, interpret what they read, and use it to their advantage when appropriate [1].

There are 2 types of reading, namely extensive and intensive reading, many definitions of benefits were given to describe these activities and researched the effectiveness on students effectiveness. Generally speaking, intensive reading refers to improving one's language skills through read-

ing while being guided by a tutor. Learning primarily takes place in the lexical and syntactic domains because the teacher exposes the pupils to unfamiliar terminology and challenging sentence patterns. In order to give the reader the chance to use a variety of reading skills, such as identifying the main idea, extracting the minor ideas, scanning for specific information, and paying close attention to specific vocabulary and grammar, intensive reading is intended to obtain detailed meaning by dealing with various aspects.

One of the first meanings offered when the term "extensive reading" is brought up is "reading a great deal of specially planned material quickly for broad comprehension with a concentration on meaning in the target language." The purpose of the material provided in comprehensive reading is to offer the pupils the chance to fairly understand it without the aid of an outside source [2].

METHODS

Nor withstanding evident ideas and undeniable researches and fact, in this paper I tried to look deep into various studies, researches, the results from surveys and questionnaires were studied carefully to take up different ideas and facts and combine with my own points of view. To utter officially more than 30 studies were collect-

ed and about half of them are given as references to provide needed information from other studies, too. Obtained data was taken from Google scholar, ERIC and Scopus sites.

RESULTS

Intensive reading.

During intensive reading, students read extensively while working on specific learning objectives and tasks. In the classroom, intensive reading tasks include scanning a text to match heads to paragraphs, scanning jumbled paragraphs and then reading them carefully to place them in the proper order, and filling in the blanks in a summary or determining whether a statement is true or incorrect [3]. Intensive reading has four learning objectives, according to Macalister (2011):

1. Emphasizing vocabulary and grammar in new language
2. Concentrating on concepts like themes and topics
3. Developing new abilities like inference-making and idea-identification
4. Paying attention to text features like coherence and genre structure [4].

There are several advantages of intensive reading;

1. Intensive reading is frequently done with challenging books that contain a lot of unfamiliar words and necessitate the use of a dictionary by the student.
2. Intensive reading improves student collaboration.
- 3- The quickest technique to pick up and absorb language is through intense reading.
- 4- It increases the power of expression.
- 5- Intensive reading is the method that is most frequently used to teach reading and reading comprehension.
- 6- It helps the student in making inferences.
- 7- It aids the learner by enabling them to comprehend sentence structure [5].

Extensive reading.

To read extensively in daily life is to read broadly and frequently. In general, exten-

sive reading refers to reading a lot of stuff to gain a comprehensive comprehension of it. The meaning of the entire text is more important to readers than the meaning of any particular words or sentences [6].

Their top ten guidelines were as follows:

1. The reading material is simple.
2. There is a wide range of reading material on numerous topics.
3. Students pick the books they want to read.
4. Students read as much as they can.
5. Reading is typically done for enjoyment, information, and general understanding.
6. Reading itself is an accomplishment.
7. Rather than being slower, reading speed is typically faster.
8. Individual and silent reading.
9. Instructors orient and direct their charges.
10. The teacher serves as a good reader role model [7].

ER is said to offer a variety of benefits, including:

1. improved language learning in areas like text structure, vocabulary, grammar, and spelling
2. a better understanding of the world
3. Enhanced writing and reading abilities
4. Reading is more enjoyable;
5. Reading is viewed more favorably
6. Increased likelihood of forming a reading habit [8].

Students generally do not have a lot of opportunities to practice their English outside of class, especially in the EFL setting. Long reading tasks will expose students to the target language far more than skills or translation assignments, which in any case require a lot of mental work in the student's native tongue. Additionally, reading widely is a fantastic way to develop schema. With this method, teachers can anticipate that their children will learn to read English not just proficiently but also with enjoyment [9] the top five priorities to assist busy teachers and enhance extensive reading abilities are as follows:

Reading is the finest approach to teach students to read and to help them become better readers.

Giving kids a say in what they read can increase their sense of agency and reading engagement.

Setting a good example for their pupils is one of the finest ways to encourage them to read and show them the enthusiasm that reading may elicit.

Re-reading is one of the best techniques to encourage reading fluency and meaningful reading.

Students frequently perform better or worse depending on how much their teachers demand of them. Therefore, educators ought to have high standards for all students and help them meet those standards [10].

DISCUSSION

The statistical analysis of this study's findings revealed a significant improvement in ESP learners' vocabulary usage scores when utilizing an intensive reading technique. It was discovered that the experimental group's pupils' pre-test mean scores were 17.72, while the students' mean scores on the post-test were 22.63. This shows that the post-mean test's scores were higher than the pre-mean test's scores, indicating that the students' scores both before and after the treatment improved [11]. According to Shen in intensive reading the schema has an essential role and while starting the reading tasks it is preferred to ask about background knowledge of the topic by asking the information about the author, the topic, headline and so on and this method called top-down processing [12].

Overall, In order to engage and encourage pupils to read, the use of intensive reading with university students attending English language programs is one alternative. Additionally, it allows subject-matter experts the chance to engage their pupils in general issues by reading a variety of literature that are relevant to their everyday lives. English language learners may also explain various parts of a work while rein-

forcing crucial information from their own experiences. To aid students in reading and comprehension, English language teachers should use a variety of reading techniques. Because teachers may not typically employ reading texts in class, this becomes important. They must be aware that reading can be beneficial in the classroom since the techniques of interpreting, linking, and forecasting can assist detect both particular and general details of the text [13].

CONCLUSION

To sum up this article, reading is the process of interpreting the information from writing text, may it be from newspaper, journal, telephone, book and so on in each types people obtain information and knowledge about something. Intensive and extensive reading types are widely used intensive reading is the reading for a specific information in detail, differently extensive way of reading is reading fast and in quantity for obtaining the general meaning. Both types are significant in language learning as, while reading learners speak and thing the language.

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ОБЗОР ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВ ИНТЕНСИВНОГО ЧТЕНИЯ И ИНТЕНСИВНОГО ЧТЕНИЯ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА НА КЛАССАХ ESL/EFL

АННОТАЦИЯ. Чтение является рецептивным навыком, который во многом помогает учащимся не только в овладении языком, но и в других сферах. В частности, есть два способа чтения: экстенсивное и интенсивное. Цель этой статьи — обсудить экстенсивное и интенсивное чтение, его преимущества в жизни каждого человека.

КЛЮЧОВЫЕ СЛОВА: чтение, пособие, экстенсивный, интенсивный.

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ESL/EFL SINFLARIDA INGLIZ TILINI O'QITISHDA EXTENSIV O'QISH VA INTENSIV O'QISHNING FOYDALARI HAQIDA SHARX

Annotatsiya. O'qish - bu o'quvchilarga nafaqat tilni o'zlashtirishda, balki turli sohalarida ko'p jihatdan yordam beradigan retseptiv qobiliyatdir. O'qishning ikkita usuli mavjud: keng va intensiv. Ushbu maqoladan maqsad ekstensiv va intensiv o'qish, uning har bir inson hayotidagi foydalarini muhokama qilishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: o'qish, foyda, ekstensiv, intensiv.